

Transformational Soft Power of Generation Z: Analysis of the Geo-Culturalization of the Landscape through Educational Initiatives and Activism

Catherine M. Roche

Patricia E. Szobonya

State University of New York, US

Abstract

Every generation is influenced by the major events occurring in the world in which they grew up, and Generation Z is no exception. Demographers concur that Generation Z members were born between the years 1997 and 2015 rendering the oldest members 24 and the youngest 6. Throughout this tumultuous era, they have experienced such catastrophic events as 9/11, numerous school and mass shootings, a severe economic downturn in 2008, and the unprecedented events of 2020--a pandemic, a recession, the killing of George Floyd with subsequent racial injustice protests, and a volatile political environment leading up to the U.S. presidential election. Despite their disillusionment and disagreement regarding how many critical issues are being addressed, Gen Z is still confident in their power to make the world a better place. Gen Z is the most educated, diverse, and technologically connected generation in history. Because of these attributes and their sheer numbers, they are able to exert their collective influence toward making change. Their activism will become even more consequential as more and more members are eligible to vote and serve in governmental policy positions. Authors will discuss Gen Z and their future as a geopolitical force to be reckoned with. Slowly emerging into the political arena and sensitive to domestic and foreign policy challenges, Gen Z will soon emerge as key players in policy decision making. The soft power of Gen Z cultivated through educational initiatives and fostered through social activism can have an integral impact on intercultural relationships and in building trust with diverse communities around the world. Virtual exchange opportunities offer unique project-based learning experiences enhancing soft power skills. Gen Z, the digital natives, embody a global platform through social media, as a vehicle of communication to unite and promote awareness of the domestic and global challenges of geo-culturalization.

Keywords: generation Z; geo-culturalization; higher education; soft power; virtual exchange

1. Introduction: Who is Generation Z?

Through their ability to influence via digital platforms and mobile devices, Generation Z (Gen Z) is redefining the global manifestation of soft power. They are commanding the attention of the broad public including empathizers, businesses, and governments around the world. With Gen Z strategically dominating virtual spaces, the traditional dynamics of soft power are being transformed around the world. The collective soft power of Gen Z is emerging and impacting economic, political, educational, and social justice agendas. Their power is charged by their ability to readily access and absorb information from around the world at an exponential rate. Pervasive technology feeds images of global encounters and inequities instantaneously to their mobile devices. These pursuits have produced the most educated and informed generation to date.¹ Witnessing more crises, catastrophes, and violence at a younger age compared to prior generations has cultivated budding activists with deep concern for human rights issues, racial inequalities, and the devastating effects of climate change. Occupying the position of being the most racially and culturally diverse generation has developed the foundation of a very accepting and socially responsive generation.² These unique characteristics deepen the desire of Gen Z to pursue an equal playing field in this geocultural landscape.

2. Geo-Culturalization and Gen Z's Soft Power

2.1. What is Soft Power?

Gen Z's candid influence and genuine empathy to make the world a better place have contributed in establishing a positive impact on global diplomacy. Influential media tactics exchanged in cyberspace serve as an integral mechanism in the contemporary

global usage of soft power. In lieu of oppressive military action, more countries are relying on their soft power to solidify their position in global markets and international relationships. Through soft power, a country focuses on the intrinsic nature of the power of persuasion to develop economic stability, political gain, and geocultural status in globalization. The current landscape encompasses not only intercontinental borders but also the infinity of cyberspace necessitating a constructive high-tech geocultural reputation. American political scientist Joseph Nye posits that “when a country is perceived as having an attractive culture and ideology, others are more willing to listen and follow.”³

However, valuable cyber reputations can deteriorate rapidly initiating backlash derived from a single unpopular post or video. As Gen Z permeates the global scene in their role as digital visionaries, they leverage power through innovation and pervasive media presence. In an article in *Forbes* David Bloom stated it best, “Gen Z represents the fast-changing face of power, a decentralized, social-media-fueled, disruptive approach embraced by young audiences of many kinds, from many places”.⁴

Younger members of Gen Z who are not yet eligible to vote can wield political power in other ways. For example, they can join organizations such as the Sunrise Movement, a political action group concerned with issues related to economic inequality, systemic racism, and climate change.⁵ This group is pressuring the U.S. government to pass legislation enabling creation of employment opportunities for all. Through their successful outreach efforts, the Sunrise Movement was instrumental in increasing the number of young people who voted in the 2020 U.S. presidential election.⁶ When members of Gen Z are elected to governmental positions, their strength will be intensified even further. Besides their use of soft power, they will be able to use newly ordained political power to create and approve legislation that defends their causes.

2.2. Soft Power Activism

Throughout history and continuing in today's politically polarized arena, power is often associated with hostility, aggression, war, and even bloodshed. Although some leaders continue to embrace these pugnacious, oppressive tactics as their dominant strategy, implementing soft power can be more effective and sustainable. Despite the current volatile, competitive geopolitical environment, leaders can heed the wishes of Gen Z to avoid these barbarous tactics when solving conflicts.

Enabled by advances in technology, communication, transportation, and trade, globalization has connected the world. Goods, people, ideas, and employment transcend geographic borders with ease, making lines in the sand less relevant. The destructive effects of climate change and the spread of virulent viruses also connect the world and are indeed profound global challenges. One of the major concerns of Gen Z is the decline of our planet and its natural resources. Because they will be inhabiting the world for many years to come, they demand confirmation that they and their progeny will have a world in which to live.

2.2.1. Environment/Climate Change

One of the most well-known activists for climate change is Swedish environmentalist Greta Thunberg. She gained notoriety in 2019 when in her emotional speech to the UN General Assembly, she berated and shamed world leaders for their failure to adequately address the existential threat of climate change. Her passionate plea was heard by her generational cohorts as evidenced by the million students around the world who walked out of classes to protest government inaction on climate change.⁷

Although Ms. Thunberg was young and determined to champion such a colossal cause, another activist was even younger. Amariyanna Copeny, also known as "Little Miss Flint," was only eight years old when she crusaded for clean water in Flint, Michigan. She contacted U.S. President Barack Obama persuading him to visit Flint to witness the situation. His visit was the catalyst that exposed the problem propelling it onto the national stage. Ms. Copeny continues her efforts related to the cause, and her actions are compatible with addressing one of the 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDGs): Goal 6 - Clean Water and Sanitation.⁸

2.2.2. Gender Equality

Another activist who gained notoriety for her courage was Malala Yousafzai, author of *I Am Malala*. In 2014 this Afghan teen was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize for her efforts against the suppression of educational opportunities for girls in Pakistan. Her advocacy for this cause provoked the Taliban resulting in her being shot while traveling on a school bus. This attack did not cease her cause but rather thrust it into the global sphere. Malala's efforts on behalf of girls aligned with two of the UN SDGs: Goal 4 - Quality Education and Goal 5 - Gender Equality.⁹

2.2.3. Political Power

In 2016 Her Excellency Shamma bint Suhail bin Faris Al Mazrui, the Minister of State for Youth Affairs in the United Arab Emirates, was the youngest government minister in the world. Her inspiring work focused on addressing problems and offering solutions to improve and empower youth and their engagement in society.¹⁰ Besides the well-known activists mentioned, many Gen Z members who are not in the public eye are making strides toward addressing one or more of the UN SDGs.¹¹ One example is Sejal Makheja. When she was 14, she collaborated with her brother

Jared to start The Elevator Project.¹² This project's goal is to lift people out of poverty by offering them job skills preparation for seeking employment. Her efforts address two UN SDGs: Goal 1 - No Poverty and Goal 8 - Decent Work and Economic Growth.¹³

2.2.4. Cultural Identity

In 2015, 11-year-old Marley Dias observed that black girls were not featured as characters in books written for girls her age. To address this issue and to encourage representation and inclusion, Ms. Dias collected and distributed 1,000 books that portrayed young black girls as characters in the stories (#1000blackgirlbooks). Three years later she published her own book entitled *Marley Dias Gets It Done: And So Can You*.¹⁴ This publication relayed an empowering message to young black female readers and aided them in constructing their own cultural identity.

In her powerful TED Talk, *Danger of a Single Story*, Nigerian writer Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie proclaimed that single stories present only one perspective. When these same stories are told repeatedly, no other perspectives are even considered. Similar to Ms. Dias, Ms. Adichie struggled to discover her cultural identity and to create her own story. She discerns a correlation between single stories and power. Individuals in power have control over what, how, who, and when stories are told. Herein lies the danger of a single story--exposure to only one point of view that becomes the one and only story told.¹⁵

2.3. Soft Power Protests

2.3.1. Black Lives Matter/Police Reform

Many people around the world are struggling with myriad issues impacting their quality of life. One of these issues is the proliferation of police shootings of individuals of color, in particular black and brown men. In May 2020 a turning point

occurred with the execution of George Floyd in Minneapolis, Minnesota. Although the Black Lives Matter (BLM) movement had already been established, this appalling murder epitomized the pervasive racial injustices rampant in the criminal justice system. This event occurred in the U.S., but its horror echoed around the world on social media posts launched by Gen Z. By July 7 the hashtag #Black Lives Matter was used on over 22 million Instagram posts.¹⁶

A survey by University of Maryland sociologist Dana Fisher and a team of researchers in New York, Washington, Los Angeles, and London reported that half the protesters surveyed were under the age of 30.¹⁷ They were non-violent, yet passionate, and offered a glimpse of hope of a much brighter future. The BLM movement in the U.S. reminded Parisians of a similar incident of police brutality in 2016 against a 24-year-old black man. Justice for Adama Traore is a movement that decried his detainment in police custody and proclaimed racial injustice in a case with obvious parallels to George Floyd.¹⁸

2.3.2. Arab Spring

The BLM movement is reminiscent of the 2011 Arab Spring, which yielded protests that swept across the Middle East in demand for social justice. Using their mobile phones primarily to post on Facebook and Twitter, activists publicized and coordinated assemblies of like-minded protesters. They uploaded videos that displayed the brutal treatment of the protesters by their respective governments. These images ignited others across the region to act and join the common cause for social equality. Social media continues to be used for public discourse and as a vehicle to exercise freedom of speech.¹⁹

2.3.3. Occupy Wall Street

The predecessors of Gen Z were the millennial generation (Generation Y), the architects of the Occupy Wall Street Movement in New York City. This movement called attention to the widening gap between the rich and the poor or the 1% and

99% respectively. The global recession of 2008-2009 illuminated the blatant effects of corporate greed, which served as the impetus for this movement. The decentralized protests began with a meme and were further energized by social media and live streaming--mechanisms that now serve as the blueprint for future movements. Hashtags were an integral element for organizing and recruiting supporters to connect and communicate. The trend has accelerated in the intervening years enabled by such ubiquitous tools as social media, mobile messaging, and other decentralizing technologies.²⁰

2.3.4. Gillets Jaune

Gillets Jaune or Yellow Vest Movement in France in 2018 focused on protests against inequality with demands for economic and social justice through political reform.²¹ A movement of this type represented a decentralized, amorphously structured, and seemingly leaderless approach. Although many adherents call their movements “leader-full,” just about everyone helps lead in some fashion. That shift has empowered many underrepresented voices and groups who previously had little access to broader public opinion or influence. Frédéric Gonthier, a political scientist at the Pacte Research Centre and the School of Political Studies in Grenoble, regarded the movement as a “watershed in French politics.”²²

2.3.5. Hong Kong

About 1.7 million Hong Kong pro-democracy protesters took to the streets to demonstrate their opposition to the Chinese government’s efforts to impose political order on the city-state. These protests ignited similar demonstrations in Thailand and inspired protesters in Myanmar. This manifestation of citizens’ discontent and anger with governments corresponds to the events that transpired in the Arab Spring.²³

The above movements all addressed a common theme--inequality in race, gender, and income plus objection to years of repression from authoritarian governments. Despite each movement's specific goals, all movements proclaim the desire for equal

treatment of all citizens. This global message is disseminated via technology, which allows for decentralization and loose structure rendering the appearance that no one individual is in charge. In reality, however, all individuals are empowered, passionate, and in control. This model of community-centered leadership is dissimilar from the U.S. civil and women's rights protests of the 1960s, movements that were organized and led by prominent activists.

2.4. Economic Soft Power

Gen Z comprises about one-third of the world's population, and their accompanying spending power of \$143 billion renders them a formidable force in the global economy. Through their soft power, they are able to change strategies and long-established practices conducted in the business world.²⁴

Marketers are aware that in order to provide value and satisfy the needs and wants of a target market, both qualitative and quantitative research is necessary. The results of research efforts will enable marketers to delve into the mindset of the consumer. Through environmental scanning of factors evident in the economic, political, technological, social, cultural, environmental, and legal areas, marketers become aware of the attitudes and behaviors of their target markets. Since consumer behavior is continually changing in our fast-paced world driven by technology, marketers must monitor the environment regularly to adapt accordingly to changing consumer tastes and preferences.

Members of Gen Y have often been described as savvy but skeptical consumers, and these characteristics can also be attributed to Gen Z. Exaggerated claims of product supremacy and aggressive sales techniques are not welcome—tactics that were frequently foisted upon naive consumers in previous decades. Gen Z does not want to be preached to and in some instances perhaps even deceived; they seek honesty and transparency in this era of alternate facts and fake news, which they are adept at deciphering.

Since they are foremost digital natives, Gen Z does not respond to traditional mass marketing advertising and promotions delivered through broadcast television and print media. Instead of these non-personalized messages, Gen Z prefers to access online visual content offered on their favorite sites such as YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok. Marketers must gain their attention quickly as attention spans are limited to only eight seconds.²⁵ However, according to *Fast Company*, this is not a negative eight-second attention span but an efficient eight-second filter enabled by a set of tools used to evaluate information in a very short time period.²⁶

2.4.1. Brands

To increase revenue and market share, marketers attempt to elevate consumers to the top level of brand loyalty called brand insistence. This highest level is characterized by repeat purchases of a brand as no substitutes will satisfy the need or want. Gen Z is converting this classic definition of brand insistence into brand enthusiasm. This shift depicts a more accurate portrayal of the Gen Z consumer, one who seeks connections to brands with the ability to play an active role in co-creation and digital content. The move also aligns with both Gen Zs entrepreneurial proclivity and desire for inclusivity and personalization.²⁷

2.4.2. Influencers

Not only in the business world but also in other sectors, power structures have been disrupted and, in some cases, dismantled entirely. Traditional structures have been replaced with new entrants whose goal is to engender trust and authenticity and thereby influence Gen Z; namely, influencers.

In previous decades celebrity endorsements and testimonials shared via mass media influenced the buying behavior and purchasing decisions of consumers. However, Gen Z is not engaged in mass media but predominantly social media. Influencers are

now designated as the new celebrity endorsers. However, an individual does not have to enjoy celebrity status to be an influencer.

The majority of Gen Z follow an influencer on social media that is relatable.²⁸ Gen Z regards influencers as individuals who can be trusted because their values align with their own. Influencers are admired and respected by their followers and serve several functions. For example, they can increase brand awareness, reach new markets, increase market share, and reinforce brands with existing customers. However, it takes time to build an image and reputation as an influencer, especially when striving to attain the highest level, a macro influencer who has amassed 100,000 to 1,000,000 followers. On the contrary, however, it does not take long to be abandoned or canceled.

2.4.3. Cancel Culture

Throughout their lifetime, Gen Z have been devoted fans of social media and have witnessed how their contemporaries have been shifting the power dynamic. Besides the celebrities who “influence” and market products bearing their eponymous names, Gen Z has observed that even ordinary people, regardless of age, have the power to endorse change when they unite and speak with a collective voice. That soft power expands when an influencer is able to take a stand on contemporary issues that matter to targeted consumer segments. The global influencer market size has more than doubled since 2019. In 2021, the market was valued at a record \$13.8 billion.²⁹ When an influencer posts an offensive tweet or photo or makes a comment that clashes with the beliefs of Gen Z, that individual will be ostracized or in more contemporary vernacular, canceled on social media. As retribution for this violation of trust and inappropriate behavior as deemed by the audience, followers will withdraw all support by ceasing to follow the individual on any social media platforms and by boycotting the brand. Even silence representing a position of

neutrality or indifference on an issue important to Gen Z can be characterized as not living up to a brand's promise and can warrant justification for cancellation.³⁰ Traditional power structures were designed in a hierarchical manner with power flowing downward. However, technology has altered this structure enabling anyone anywhere with a social media account to deploy influence. The soft power of the U.S. has spread the notion of cancel culture abroad. For example, an individual from the U.S. gave an interview for a Dutch media outlet in the Netherlands on the positive and negative aspects of cancel culture. The interview discussed how some individuals use cancel culture to elevate their own positions through the defamation of others. Although the interview received many positive responses, it was removed or "canceled" because it displayed too much sympathy toward the victims of cancel culture.³¹

2.4.4. Fast Fashion and Sustainability

The damaging effect of fast fashion on the environment, which leaves a larger carbon footprint, is another aspect of sustainability that worries Gen Z. A concomitant issue is the violation of human rights often associated with the manufacture of clothing. Manufacturing has been offshored to factories in countries where the cost of labor is less than in the U.S. According to the 2015 documentary, *The True Cost*, the fashion industry is one of the most labor-intensive industries employing one out of six people on the planet, many of whom are female. However, according to reports from NGOs such as Oxfam, Human Rights Watch, and the ILRF, fewer than 2% of workers earn a living wage.³²

Garments are mass produced in factories, some of which lack safety protocols in addition to absent or weak legislation protecting worker rights. Besides the violation of human rights by not providing a living wage to reduce poverty, the environment is also a victim.³³

Gen Z is aware that 26 billion pounds of textiles end up in landfills each year. Instead of purchasing new clothing, Gen Z may rent clothing or patronize secondhand or thrift stores. This response saves both money and the environment while providing Gen Z consumers with the opportunity to display their individuality through the unique assortment of clothing available for purchase.³⁴

2.4.5. Investing and Environmental, Social, Governance (ESG)

Awareness of and advocacy for sustainability was launched by Gen Y, and this struggle is being pursued by Gen Z. Therefore, they are selective in choosing where to invest their earnings. Just as Gen Z prefers to transact business with companies whose mission statements and actions concur with their own goals, Gen Z wants to invest in companies that exhibit a strong commitment to social responsibility. Their investment choices prioritize companies that promote ESG (environmental, social, and governance) practices. Since Gen Z demands the truth and is capable of dismissing fake news, they can easily detect greenwashing, a term used to describe companies that preach sustainability yet do not actually engage in requisite behavior.³⁵

2.4.6. Co-opetition

Despite differences in cultural, economic, and political environments around the world, Gen Z recognizes that we all experience some of the same problems in our daily lives. Only through partnerships can we attempt to address and solve issues that affect quality of life, basic human rights, and ultimately survival. UN SDG Goal 17 - Partnerships for the Goals underscores the need for participation of governments, public and private sector businesses, non-profits, NGOs, and other entities in devising solutions to fulfill all UN SDGs by 2030.

Advances made in the Fourth Industrial Revolution arising from the rapid acceleration of artificial intelligence plus changes attributed to the relentless pandemic have increased our dependence on global network platforms. All of us—

especially Gen Z—rely on these ubiquitous platforms for communication, entertainment, commerce, education, transportation, information, etc. Through their scale, purpose, and popularity, these networks serve as instruments of geopolitics, spawning a battleground where they compete for hegemony in fields such as science, medicine, finance, and politics.

Nations often assume a competitive stance when solving issues unilaterally through their execution of hard power accompanied by domestic nationalism. However, adopting a paradigm called co-opetition can be more advantageous and sustainable. Each nation enjoys certain competitive advantages. When these advantages are combined with the dissimilar strengths of other nations, a viable solution for all stakeholders may be discovered and implemented. This blend of competition and cooperation, aptly named co-opetition, is a form of soft power that has been used successfully by both companies and countries. Omnipresent challenges and opportunities enable nations to work together for the common good and prosperity of all citizens. Gen Z is ready, willing, and able to rise to the challenge.³⁶

3. Maximizing Soft Power Through Higher Education

Gen Z are asserting dominance in a digital savvy expanding network of globally minded peers. They have discovered their own soft power of influence in their social and business engagements. Despite the unprecedented disruptions in daily life caused by COVID-19, Gen Z were already accustomed to navigating easily between the physical and digital worlds. They were comfortable pursuing education in alternative formats, seeking entertainment, working, shopping, and communicating in an existing digital paradigm. Notwithstanding their appreciation for face-to-face interactions, they continue to flourish in a virtual world.

Post-pandemic geo-educational challenges call for skills that support the digital needs of Gen Z students in an accelerated tech environment. Current and future higher education professionals will need to focus on developing individualized

learning and student-centered approaches in the classroom and in digital spaces. As online intercultural dialogue continues to increase, so does the need for soft skills that are designed to enrich and sustain impactful conversations. Business and global trends further demand cultural sensitivity skills to effectuate community building. Twenty-first century soft skills such as influence, communication, adaptability, emotional intelligence and cultural sensitivity are vital in building reliable, transparent relationships.³⁷

3.1 Developing 21st Century Skills

Contemporary education plays an essential role in guiding Gen Z's influential soft power. Despite the rising costs of pursuing a college education, Gen Z continues to be the most educated generation to date. A higher-ed geo-educational framework should underscore the interconnectedness of economic, social, political and environmental issues to meet the demands of today's societies that transcend international borders.³⁸ By using a geo-centric approach, educators can focus on student community building through global and contemporary competencies. Global competence is the ability to understand local, global and intercultural issues and to develop an appreciation of multicultural perspectives and alternative viewpoints.³⁹ It includes interacting with people from different cultures for their collective well-being and encouraging sustainable development around the world.⁴⁰

Hands-on inclusive teaching methods that are integrated into the curriculum foster student interactions within the global community.⁴¹ Contemporary teaching requires educators to develop such global competencies and activities that advance them. Educators should make a deliberate effort to include updated pedagogical strategies that ensure inclusive and equitable learning. Since students possess different learning abilities and preferred learning styles, integrating individualized, personalized, and universal design for learning principles will benefit all students.

With expanding globalization capabilities, it is critical that students be equipped with the social consciousness to effectively communicate and adapt in our multicultural transformative future.⁴² Geo-education prepares students not only to critically analyze and problem solve but also to actively listen to their peers' ideas, respect unfamiliar opinions, and ultimately work cooperatively toward solutions. Intercultural discourse bolsters students' confidence and curiosity, while dissolving social and cultural barriers.⁴³

3.1.1. Fake News

Gen Z is exposed to a multitude of information daily. Therefore, the ability to identify fake news is critical when navigating digital media and news outlets. Fake news is often written by non-experts and offers no reliable sources. Therefore, this information cannot readily be located on any credible sites as it is solely opinion-based. In addition, fake news typically is used to deceptively appeal to human emotions and is often spread to delegitimize political parties. Gen Z is not immune from believing and sharing misguided information.⁴⁴ The false or unfair equal balance journalists provide for certain stories contribute to misleading coverage.⁴⁵ For example, when the BBC reported on a piece surrounding society's contribution to climate change, the BBC also devoted significantly more time to stories from individuals who denied that human contribution had any effect on the current climate.⁴⁶ When scientific evidence clearly supports one side, but journalism provides more or equal attention to both sides by non-scientific experts, confusion and distrust prevail.⁴⁷

Higher education can be instrumental in preparing students to utilize their inquisitive intellect while surfing the Internet. Educators can assign research opportunities in which students investigate the origins of various ideologies to gain a baseline understanding. By using a critical approach, facts that may require additional authentication are flagged for further inquiry. Students can learn how to confirm

reputable primary sources, which would assist in identifying misinformation and false statements. Research and due diligence in fact checking can aid students in comprehending the underlying context of the material enabling an informed decision--truth or fiction.⁴⁸ While fake news is a serious concern, the underlying essence of a polarized society may require further examination as the root cause for the dissemination of fake news.⁴⁹

3.1.2. Emotional Intelligence

An effective communicator is an individual who possesses a high level of emotional intelligence (EQ). Gen Z engages in interminable communications online; therefore, a high level of EQ is paramount. One of the elements of EQ is self-awareness, which enables individuals to know how to appropriately control their feelings in certain circumstances.⁵⁰ Besides self-awareness, EQ also involves the ability to be aware of and consider another individual's emotional state. Sensing emotions in others prepares one to act accordingly within those specific encounters. The more interactions one has, the more likely emotional signals can be interpreted. Confidence and self-esteem can increase and contribute to one's ability to share on an emotional level. Educational models often focus on the intellect of students but not necessarily on their emotional aptitude.⁵¹ In order to foster development of EQ, the curriculum can be infused with socio-emotional competencies that assess students' empathetic ability and compassion.⁵²

Empathy, another element of EQ, is equally important for global citizenry. Possessing empathy enables one to relate to another person in their specific situation, such as putting yourself in their shoes and viewing an issue from their perspective. When individuals fail to recognize or feel empathy for others, resolving problems or reaching agreements can be difficult and often impossible. Through inadvertent miscommunications and misunderstandings, business and personal relationships can be further complicated when connecting with culturally diverse individuals. The

World Economic Forum (WEF) underscores the importance of EQ for successful communications in the workplace and recognizes that understanding cultural norms and social cues contribute to stronger working relationships.⁵³

As lockdowns spread across the globe in 2020 and 2021 demanding isolation, ironically citizens of the world felt a sense of collectiveness. A shared empathy for the crisis affecting all of us, albeit some more than others, was detected. Ultimately, we were united by this ubiquitous disease that was ravaging the world, and we sought opportunities to connect and share our experiences collectively.⁵⁴

3.1.3. Cultural Intelligence

As a result of the issues of systemic racism being acknowledged around the world, diversity, equity, inclusion, and social justice have garnered much attention in business and academia. However, a prerequisite for integrating these initiatives is to develop cultural intelligence. Cultural intelligence (CQ) is the ability to relate and work effectively in culturally diverse situations.⁵⁵

In addition to emotional intelligence, cultural intelligence (CQ) is also a skill valued in today's multicultural environment. Individuals who possess high levels of CQ are able to regard an individual who is a member of a culture different from their own not simply as a member of a stereotypical group but as a unique human being. The cultural environment an individual is raised in aids in the development of daily structure, influence, behavior, and expectations of societal members.⁵⁶ These observations and interactions assist one in understanding, interpreting, and expressing their emotional responses.⁵⁷ When one is exposed to a variety of cultures, one develops *cultural regulation*, the alignment of emotions with certain cultural values, ideals, goals and concerns of others.⁵⁸ As emotional experiences differ across cultures, exposure to a variety of cultures early on is essential for developing this competency.⁵⁹

In order to cultivate students' cultural identity, educators should recognize the social fabric of their student population. Professional development that focuses on the culture and customs of the institution, the community, surrounding areas, and the students should be offered to educators. This training will enable them to tailor contextualized local, social and global cultural customs in projects, resulting in students' deeper understanding of culture and themselves.

3.1.4. Curriculum Innovations

Pragmatic Gen Z has expectations that education will prepare them for employment in the real world. Experiential learning, project-based learning, and/or mentorship programs provide practical learning by doing, beyond lecture-based learning. The juxtaposition of the workforce is a result of the pandemic—initially employees losing jobs due to lockdowns and illness and now employees quitting jobs (the Great Resignation) for a variety of reasons. Gen Z is interested in work that offers a work/life balance, work that is purposeful and resonates with their ambitions, values, and goals.

Higher education can offer skill-based learning to meet the demands of business. Educators should employ teaching methods that deliver skills transferable to workforce opportunities. The traditional lecture method passively dispenses content knowledge and does not address the essential soft skills necessary for future employment. In addition, easy access to knowledge through search engines such as Google, numerous free online resources, and third-party content providers further decries the effectiveness of the lecture method.⁶⁰ Therefore, it is imperative that contemporary education include mixed instructional methods designed for individualized learning such as student-centered, inquiry-based, interactive, and collaborative projects. These innovative active learning strategies provide the hands-on opportunities that Gen Z are seeking for seamless transition to the workforce. A recent study of 6,000 members of Gen Z indicated two key areas of education that

need improvement: “greater exposure to real-life work (59%) and professional mentorship (57%)”.⁶¹

For example, in modernizing the law school Socratic lecture method, inclusion of a skill-set approach could offer students a practical hands-on experience.⁶² Through simulated activities students can conduct client and witness interviews, draft complaints, negotiate a mock settlement, or participate in a mock trial and a moot court. Assuming the role of legal counsel from inception to trial gives students a realistic preview of a day in the life of an attorney.

3.1.5. Alternative Formats

The emergence of COVID-19 and the continuing spread of its variants has rapidly changed the delivery of education to include more digital remote platforms. A positive and perhaps permanent result of the pandemic is the mobility and flexibility that digital learning offers. For example, students who are not able to travel to campus for a variety of reasons can save commuting time enabling an improved work-life harmony.⁶³

Hyflex learning, a recently popularized format, offers students the choice of either face-to-face instruction in a physical classroom or synchronous remote instruction. The instructor teaches from the classroom to students in attendance while a camera and microphone follow the instructor to deliver the lesson to the remote students. Because of the instructor’s ability to utilize tech tools to engage all students regardless of location, this method supports an equitable approach to learning. In addition, students may select the venue that is optimal for their learning preferences and styles. To deliver Hyflex instruction, however, institutions must not only finance purchase of the necessary equipment but also train faculty to use the system effectively.⁶⁴

3.1.6. Virtual Exchange

Virtual exchanges enable students to work with students in other countries in a project-based learning environment empowered by technology. In the past international student collaborations through study abroad have served as the conventional vehicle through which students were able to demonstrate soft power. With travel restrictions constantly changing as a result of pandemic variants sweeping the globe, incorporating virtual exchange activities serve many purposes. The intercultural relationships between countries, partnering institutions, faculty, and participating students can be reinforced; and these relationships can serve as the pandemic approach to manifestation of soft power around the globe.

Virtual exchange is an instructor-led, team-teaching approach used to invoke discourse and constructive engagement on issues involving local and global challenges. In a co-facilitated learning environment, a project is developed with tasks spanning a period of several weeks to an entire semester. This activity is designed to build students' confidence as they interact in different educational, social, and cultural situations. Students create an atmosphere of trust when they share their unique perspectives, beliefs, values, and behaviors. Students also develop the ability to have an open mind and master the art of listening to alternative views.⁶⁵

An excellent, relevant method to unite a cohort of international students is through a virtual exchange project focusing on one or more of the UN SDGs.⁶⁶

Project-based learning opportunities involving the UN SDGs raise awareness of global problems and present an opportunity for students to initiate positive action around the globe.

3.1.7. Virtual Exchange Examples

Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL) is a State University of New York (SUNY) initiative established in 2006. The goal of COIL is to engage students in cross-cultural communication and collaboration with students from other institutions around the world. Through co-facilitated project-based tasks delivered

in a team-oriented learning environment, students are given the opportunity to develop 21st century skills necessary for employment and existence in a globalized world.⁶⁷

The Stevens Initiative was established in 2015 to honor the legacy of former U.S. Ambassador J. Christopher Stevens who was killed in the attack on the U.S. Embassy in Benghazi, Libya. He was a staunch, passionate supporter of international education with a penchant for the Middle East North Africa (MENA) region in particular.⁶⁸

Through multilevel partnerships with governments, corporations, foundations, and the U.S. Dept. of State, the Stevens Initiative offered several grants through which Ambassador Stevens' commitment to fortify relationships in this region could continue. The Stevens Grant was divided into three cohorts spanning the years 2016 to 2017, and COIL was one of the grant recipients. Select SUNY and MENA faculty participants attended online professional development workshops in preparation for collaboration. After partnerships were established, partners traveled to either Cairo (Cohort 2) or Beirut (Cohort 3) for face-to-face partner introductions, meetings, and additional training. After the training was completed, U.S. faculty visited the campuses of their MENA partners in Cairo, Egypt; Beirut, Lebanon; and Oujda, Morocco, to continue collaboration discussions and preparations.

Global Solutions is another virtual exchange program that is supported by the Stevens Initiative and administered by the Aspen Institute. International Research and Exchanges Board (IREX) is an independent nonprofit organization that offers the program to higher education institutions in Iraq, Jordan, and the U.S.⁶⁹

Although the basic goals are similar to COIL in terms of strengthening relationships and developing intercultural soft skills in preparation for employment, Global Solutions focuses exclusively on three countries. One of the programs offered is the

Global Solutions Sustainability Challenge, a prescribed curriculum with defined milestones and deliverables to be achieved within an eight-week period. Training workshops and ongoing support are offered to prepare faculty partners; but unlike COIL, partnerships are assigned not self-selected. The focus of the Challenge is on sustainability, an issue that is of paramount importance to Gen Z and one that addresses many of the UN SDGs.⁷⁰ Besides the intrinsic motivation that results from participation in experiential learning—researching a problem and offering a feasible solution to a global issue—teams awarded first, second, and third place are provided with funding to finance implementation of their solutions.⁷¹

3.2. Integrating Diversity, Inclusion, and Equity in the Curriculum

3.2.1. Decolonization

Gen Z appreciates an authentic education rich in history that includes all perspectives and embraces diversity. Lessons that include historic triumphs yet also address the nefariousness of colonizers and conquerors serve to broaden the understanding of the complexities of all peoples. Decolonization is the process of adding the voices of indigenous peoples while removing colonial and Western influence and subjugation.⁷² Current educational systems that lack a balanced portrayal diminish the representation of indigenous people's culture, hardships, survival and endurance.⁷³

Decolonization of the curriculum suggests a deconstruction of colonial ideology that typically can be found in textbooks and resources and within traditional teaching methodologies. A whitewashed curriculum incorporates Western teaching philosophies and tends to provide inaccuracies or omissions of important historical events, usually rendering the stories more palatable. The failure to accurately portray historical truths subtly perpetuates the inequality in education.⁷⁴ Lessons that lack stories about indigenous peoples and marginalized populations affect student

engagement and ability to learn.⁷⁵ Students perform better when they are able to relate to stories that resonate with them and their heritage. Understanding the necessary racial context can support students as they feel heard, seen, and valued resulting in an equitable and inclusive learning environment.

Decolonizing the curriculum can enhance the development of one's critical consciousness.⁷⁶ Students inquire and analyze beyond the written text and identify the subtle biases and assumptions plagued within the contextualization of stories. Identification of lessons that perpetuate Western approaches and superiority are scrutinized and reflected upon for change.⁷⁷ Decolonizing education extends beyond just the curriculum as it includes incorporating individualized learning methods and ensuring that the climate of the institution is equitable and inclusive.⁷⁸ Gen Z seeks to challenge the imbalance of educational power dynamics and are willing to use their soft power of persuasion to expose a diversified narrative. Gen Z's digital aptitude enables them to create digital spaces that inspire conversation surrounding the demobilization of these oppressive systems.⁷⁹

3.2.2. Critical Race Theory

Critical race theory (CRT) and decolonization are closely related topics, but they have some notable differences. CRT is often confused by many as an academic discipline or subject. However, CRT is more appropriately defined as a practice of unmasking deeply embedded racial injustices in legal contexts.⁸⁰ Law professors learned that the justice system had played a pivotal role in the perpetuation of inequality through its law making and continues to contribute to the oppression of historically marginalized populations. Court decisions seemingly appear to resolve certain injustices, but the continuing results show an unequal outcome for marginalized groups. For example, the Civil Rights Act of 1964 was enacted to end racial discrimination in the United States; however, racial inequities continue

today.⁸¹ Exploring CRT forces one to take a deeper dive into questioning why racism still exists within law and other institutions such as education, healthcare, and the financial system. CRT aims to challenge the fundamental source of policies in these institutions and determine what requisite change is necessary. CRT also acknowledges that law can impact positive change and enhance the upward mobility of historically marginalized populations.⁸²

3.2.3. Culturally Responsive Teaching

In 1992 educational theorist Gloria Ladson-Billings coined the term *culturally relevant pedagogy*. Through her classroom experiences and subsequent research, she recommended that instruction focus on three student goals: academic success, cultural competence, and socio-political awareness. Attainment of these goals would empower all students, especially members from marginalized groups (Culturally Responsive Teaching). Building upon her research, another educational theorist, Geneva Gay, coined a term widely recognized today, *culturally responsive teaching*. Her 2001 award-winning publication entitled *Culturally Responsive Teaching: Theory, Research, and Practice* proposes that students will perform better when teaching is relevant to their lives and is filtered through their own cultural experiences.⁸³

Both scholars regard the integration of student culture and background into all aspects of education to be a valued asset rather than a deficiency or liability to be resolved. Project-based learning focused on solving real world problems that emanate from oppression of marginalized students will enable all students to examine issues through their own cultural lenses. As a result, learning will be more relevant and effective in engaging a diverse population and will comply with diversity, equity, inclusion, and social justice educational reforms.

4. Conclusion

Increased utilization of technology, persistent effects of COVID-19, and omnipresent Gen Z have impacted how our nations can navigate toward a geo-cultural, equitable, and sustainable future. Gen Z has already begun to shape the future of the social, political, and economic structure of the global landscape. Their activism, tenets, and practices continue to influence outcomes in local, global and digital spaces. Gen Z's soft power has already been revealed as a vital tool in building global partnerships and resolving global challenges. Gen Z can make a difference in the world without using coercive force, which is often the prevailing approach in foreign policy diplomacy.

The role of education is the conduit to guide this resilient, passionate population towards building a global community through international connections. Educators should continue to facilitate skill-based culturally immersive experiences to prepare Gen Z to use their soft power toward foreign policy challenges. Emphasizing competencies such as cultural sensitivity, emotional intelligence, diversity, equity, and inclusion through virtual exchange will enable higher education faculty in producing socially interconnected, culturally responsible citizens.

Gen Z has undoubtedly transformed the indelible nature of soft power and will continue to crusade in their quest for global consciousness. To achieve their ambitious goals, co-opetition should be considered as a feasible strategy for implementation.

Endnotes

[1] Fry, R., & Parker, K. (2020, August 14). *'post-millennial' generation on track to be most diverse, best educated*. Pew Research Center's Social & Demographic Trends Project. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2018/11/15/early-benchmarks-show-post-millennials-on-track-to-be-most-diverse-best-educated-generation-yet/>

[2] Fry, R., & Parker, K.

[3] Li, E. (2018, August 20). *The rise and fall of Soft Power*. Foreign Policy. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://foreignpolicy.com/2018/08/20/the-rise-and-fall-of-soft-power>

[4] Bloom, D. (2019, October 6). *How gen Z and millennials are reshaping what power is, and what it means for brands*. Forbes. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/dbloom/2019/09/12/how-gen-z-and-millennials-are-reshaping-what-power-is-and-what-it-means-for-brands/?sh=726d434f6d9f>

[5] Sunrise Movement. *We are the Climate Revolution*. Sunrise Movement. (2021, December 15). Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.sunrisemovement.org/>. A U.S. youth movement enacting change through people and political power with a focus on the Green New Deal.

[6] Sunrise Movement. Members of the movement contacted 65 million voters through postcards, texts, and calls resulting in the largest youth voting turnout in history.

[7] Cranley, E. (2019, October 1). *These 10 young activists are trying to move the Needle on climate change, gun control, and other global issues*. Insider. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.insider.com/young-activists-climate-change-guns-greta-thunberg-2019-9>. Ms. Thunberg has spoken at global events such as the World Economic Forum, the British Parliament, the U.S. Congress, the UN Climate Summits COP25 and more recently COP26. She began #FridaysforFuture, a youth-organized and led global movement, to pressure lawmakers to take climate change seriously and to listen to the scientists.

[8] United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development | department of economic and social affairs*. United Nations. Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>. Sustainable development refers to development that considers the economic and environmental well-being of future generations. In 2015 the United Nations General Assembly unanimously approved a new development framework to address the shortcomings of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs): seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Three main characteristics distinguish the SDGs from the MDGs: sustainability, interconnectedness, and a global focus. These goals are based on more equitable and inclusive societies, with solid institutions, with full equality between men and women, and through local, national, and international alliances.

[9] United Nations. (2015).

[10] Simmons A. (2017, March 8). *Q&A: United Arab Emirates' 23-year-old minister of Youth Affairs has high aspirations for her peers*. Los Angeles Times. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.latimes.com/world/global-development/la-fg-global-uae-youth-minister-20170302-story.html>. According to the CIA World Factbook, the median age in the UAE is 30. The work of the Minister of State for Youth Affairs is critical in reaching and engaging a young demographic cohort.

[11] United Nations. (2015).

[12] The elevator project - about Us. *theelevatorproject*. (n.d.). Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://www.theelevatorproject.org/about-us>

[13] United Nations. (2015).

[14] McGrath, M. (2021, June 29). *From activist to author: How 12-year-old Marley Dias is changing the face of Children's Literature*. Forbes. Retrieved March 29, 2022, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/maggiemcgrath/2017/06/13/from-activist-to-author-how-12-year-old-marley-dias-is-changing-the-face-of-childrens-literature/?sh=41ffb9e44ce0>

[15] Adichie, C. N. (2009, July) *The danger of a single story*. Facing History and Ourselves. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.facinghistory.org/holocaust-and-human-behavior/chapter-1/danger-single-story>. View TED Talk of same name.

[16] Wulforst, E. (2020, July 9). *How Generation Z is Propelling the Black Lives Matter Movement*. Two River Times. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://tworivertimes.com/how-generation-z-is-propelling-the-black-lives-matter-movement/>

[17] Fisher, D. (2020, June 7). *I'm a professor who studies protests and activism. here's why the George Floyd protests are different*. Business Insider. Retrieved March 29, 2022, from <https://www.businessinsider.com/protests-activism-professor-why-george-floyd-movement-is-different-2020-6>

[18] Walt, V. (2020, December 11). *Assa Traoré and France's fight for racial justice*. Time. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://time.com/5919814/guardians-of-the-year-2020-assa-traore/>

[19] Brown, H., Guskin, E., & Mitchell, A. (2019, December 31). *The role of social media in the Arab uprisings*. Pew Research Center's Journalism Project. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.pewresearch.org/journalism/2012/11/28/role-social-media-arab-uprisings/>

[20] Captain, S. (2021, September 15). *How occupy wall street spawned a decade of protest, politics, and Social Media*. Fast Company. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.fastcompany.com/90675586/occupy-wall-street-tenth-anniversary>

[21] Lichfield, J. (2019, February 9). *Just who are the gilets jaunes?* The Guardian. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/feb/09/who-really-are-the-gilets-jaunes>

[22] Dodman, B. (2019, November 16). *A year of insurgency: How yellow vests left 'indelible mark' on French politics*. France 24. Retrieved March 29, 2022, from <https://www.france24.com/en/20191116-a-year-of-insurgency-how-yellow-vests-left-indelible-mark-on-french-politics>

[23] Yuan, L. (2019, August 20). *China's soft-power failure: Condemning Hong Kong's protests*. The New York Times. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/08/20/business/china-hong-kong-social-media-soft-power.html>

[24] Salukov, D. (2021, December 7). *Gen Z Influencer Marketing: Everything you need to know*. Insense. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://insense.pro/blog/gen-z-influencer-marketing-everything-you-need-to-know>. And Celeste. (2019, November 30). How millennials and gen Z are investing sustainably. How Millennials and Gen Z are investing sustainably. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://inyova.ch/en/expertise/en/millennials-gen-z-and-sustainable-investing/>

[25] Finch, J. (2015, May 4). *What is generation Z, and what does it want?* Fast Company. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://www.fastcompany.com/3045317/what-is-generation-z-and-what-does-it-want>

[26] Finch, J. (2015, May 4).

[27] Chohan, S. (n.d.). *Influencer marketing for gen Z: 4 keys to success*. linkfluence.png. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.linkfluence.com/blog/influencer-marketing-for-gen-z>

[28] Freer, A. (2020, March 8). *89% of young people follow 'relatable' influencers*. Business of Apps. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://www.businessofapps.com/news/89-of-young-people-follow-relatable-influencers/> The majority of respondents reported that they wanted to follow influencers who shared global concerns.

[29] Statista Research Department, & 14, O. (2021, October 14). *Global Influencer Market Size 2021*. Statista. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1092819/global-influencer-market-size/>

[30] Gerstmann, E. (2021, December 10). *Cancel culture is only getting worse*. Forbes. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/evangerstmann/2020/09/13/cancel-culture-is-only-getting-worse/?sh=3a509b9463f4>. Cancel culture is a form of ostracization and also perhaps a violation of freedom of speech.

[31] Henderson, R. (2021, November 18). *America exports cancel culture to the world*. Quillette. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://quillette.com/2020/07/02/america-exports-cancel-culture-to-the-world/>. Since the virtual world is global with no physical geographic borders, cancel culture can be ubiquitous.

[32] Oxfam Australia. *What she makes*. Oxfam Australia. (2021, December 6). Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.oxfam.org.au/what-she-makes/>. Oxfam's What She Makes campaign demands big clothing brands pay the women who make clothing a living wage.

[33] Thomas, D. (2019, August 29). *The high price of Fast Fashion*. The Wall Street Journal. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from https://www.wsj.com/articles/the-high-price-of-fast-fashion-11567096637?mod=article_inline. The catastrophic factory fire and building collapse in Bangladesh in 2012 and 2013 indicate that worker safety measures were not being followed. In 2015 the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) reported that Americans sent 10.5 million tons of textiles to landfills that year. Most synthetics used in the manufacture of clothing are not biodegradable.

[34] Bloomberg. (2021, February 3). *Majority of Generation Z investors identify Green and Sustainable investing as the biggest trend of 2021*. Bloomberg.com. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://www.bloomberg.com/company/press/majority-of-generation-z-investors-identify-green-and-sustainable-investing-as-the-biggest-trend-of-2021/>. Thredup resale report indicates that more than 40 percent of millennials and Gen Z shoppers have shopped for secondhand clothing and accessories during the past year. Nearly two in five thrifters say they are replacing fast fashion purchases with secondhand clothing. Forty-five percent of millennials and Gen Z say they refuse to buy from "non-sustainable" brands and retailers. See Inc., T. (n.d.). *2021 fashion resale market and trend report*. thredUP. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from https://www.thredup.com/resale/?mkt_tok=MjExLU5KWS0xNjUAAAF_tt2t-Cbo-INnOrNXAn2Jey4Br0SIk3vt9K8FMXRe9PBjJin37PN7DTR8wkJ7HioM2WuQyEV5KY1Wur2eoDAPB508kogG4AMrmZEE_AIc-aKvH6o#whos-thrifting-and-why

[35] Bloomberg. (2021, February 3). Bloomberg hosted an inaugural “Next-Gen Connect” event with TARA and GAIN to connect top investors with university students across Asia, Europe and the Middle East.

[36] Brandenburger, A., & Nalebuff, B. (2020, December 15). *The rules of co-opetition*. Harvard Business Review. Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://hbr.org/2021/01/the-rules-of-co-opetition> and Cheng, Y. (2021, May 6). What is 'coopetition' and how can international organizations help? World Economic Forum. Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/05/what-is-coopetition-and-how-can-international-organizations-help/>

[37] Landau, J. (2018, October 17). *Council post: Why cultural sensitivity should be a forethought, not an afterthought*. Forbes. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesnycouncil/2018/10/17/why-cultural-sensitivity-should-be-a-forethought-not-an-afterthought/>. See for further explanation of cultural sensitivity.

[38] National Geographic Society. (2012, October 9). *The global network*. National Geographic Society. Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/article/global-network/>

[39] PISA. (2018). *Global competence - PISA*. OECD. Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/innovation/global-competence/>. Created by OECD, PISA assesses skills such as collaborative problem solving and global competence. PISA is also investigating opportunities to assess other related skills such as creative thinking.

[40] PISA. (2018). Global competence supports the SDGs. PISA reviews global curricula and examines students' ability to apply knowledge and skills and to analyze, reason, and communicate effectively as they solve problems.

[41] Vander Ark, T. (2017, September 5). *Educating for global competence: 6 reasons, 7 competencies, 8 strategies, 9 innovations*. Getting Smart. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.gettingsmart.com/2017/09/05/educating-for-global-competence-6-reasons-7-competencies-8-strategies-9-innovations/> See framework to develop global and cultural competencies. Project-based learning enables development of intercultural competence and brings awareness to the UN SDGs on both a global and local level.

[42] Hughes, E. (2020, January 10). *The future of work is creative collaboration*. Management. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.management-issues.com/opinion/7369/the-future-of-work-is-creative-collaboration/>. Businesses surveyed by WEF reported that in 2022 the most in-demand skills will be analytical thinking and innovation; active learning and learning strategies; and creativity, originality and initiative. Creative collaboration is the common thread that applies to all three of these skills enabling workers to be contributing members of teams and interconnected networks.

[43] Levy, F., & Murnane, R. J. (2006). *Why the changing American economy calls for twenty-first century learning: answers to educators' questions*. Europe PMC. Retrieved December 18, 2021, <https://europepmc.org/article/med/17017257American>. Educational reforms commensurate with American employment opportunities elaborated.

[44] Dans, E. (2020, September 15). *You are wrong if you think generation Z is "Immune" to fake news*. Forbes. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/enriquedans/2020/09/15/you-are-wrong-if-you-think-generation-z-is-immune-to-fake-news/?sh=331e5414314e>.

[45] Grimes, D. R. (2016, November 8). *Impartial journalism is laudable. but false balance is dangerous*. The Guardian. Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.theguardian.com/science/blog/2016/nov/08/impartial-journalism-is-laudable-but-false-balance-is-dangerous>

[46] Grimes, D. R. (2016, November 8).

[47] Grimes, D. R. (2016, November 8). For example, the claim that the MMR vaccine is connected to autism caused much confusion.

[48] Dans, E. (2020, September 15).

[49] Osmundsen, M., Petersen, M. B., & Bor, A. (2021, May 13). *How partisan polarization drives the spread of fake news*. Brookings. Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.brookings.edu/techstream/how-partisan-polarization-drives-the-spread-of-fake-news>. See study on Twitter usage in the US and the spread of fake news.

[50] Bradberry, T. (2017). *Emotional intelligence: What it is and Why you need it*. World Economic Forum. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2017/02/why-you-need-emotional-intelligence/>

[51] Miladinovic, M. (2018, August 28). *Emotional intelligence is the basis for global competence*. carlostest2. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://carlostest2.afssite.afs.org/2018/05/15/emotional-intelligence-is-the-basis-for-global-competence/?lang=en>

[52] Miladinovic, M. (2018, August 28).

[53] Bradberry, T. (2017). See study on EQ as the strongest predictor of performance. See Hohaia, M. (2019, September 26). *Emotional intelligence: No longer a 'nice to have' but an essential skill in the workplace*. Thrive Global. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://thriveglobal.com/stories/emotional-intelligence-no-longer-a-nice-to-have-but-an-essential-skill-in-the-workplace/>. WEF lists 10 skills needed to survive in the workplace. Although emotional intelligence is #6, the author contends that it should be #1 as attainment of this skill impacts all the others.

[54] AFS Intercultural Programs. (2017). *Collaboration, empathy and self-awareness are key skills*. AFS Intercultural Programs. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://afs.org/2017/04/19/collaboration-empathy-and-self-awareness-are-key-skills-of-global-citizens-an-afs-forum-concludes/>

[55] Pretorius, Q., Merry, T., & Center, C. I. (2021, November 8). *Cultural intelligence training: Cultural intelligence center*. Cultural Intelligence Center - We provide research-based, innovative solutions for assessing, predicting, and improving cultural intelligence (CQ). Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://culturalq.com/about-cultural-intelligence/culture/>. Cultural intelligence supersedes cultural sensitivity and awareness. Cultural intelligence encompasses four capabilities: drive, knowledge, action, and strategy.

[56] Pretorius, Q., Merry, T., & Center, C. I. (2021, November 8).

[57] Pretorius, Q., Merry, T., & Center, C. I. (2021, November 8).

[58] De Leersnyder, J., Boiger, M., & Mesquita, B. (2013). Cultural regulation of emotion: individual, relational, and structural sources. *Frontiers in psychology*, 4, 55. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00055>. The quality of a relationship varies from culture to culture. Distinguishing between individualistic and collective cultures will contribute to better understanding.

[59] De Leersnyder, J., Boiger, M., & Mesquita, B. (2013). See as cultural differences in emotion regulation are elaborated.

[60] Ko, D. (2021, January). *How gen Z redefines media consumption habits - think with google apac*. Google. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/intl/en-apac/consumer-insights/consumer-trends/stay-woke-how-gen-z-teaching-us-about-future-news-and-information/>. Gen Z consults multiple sources for information and fact checking. Preferred channels are Facebook, Google, and YouTube.

[61] Sawyer, A. (2021). *What businesses and gen Z have to offer each other*. World Economic Forum. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/06/business-education-gen-z-global-challenges-future>. See article for further key findings in survey results.

[62] Lii, B. (2008, September). (PDF) *the Elephant in law school classrooms: Overuse of ...* The Elephant in Law School Classrooms: Overuse of the Socratic Method as an Obstacle to Teaching Modern Law Students. Retrieved March 29, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228155379_The_Elephant_in_Law_School_Classrooms_Overuse_of_the_Socratic_Method_as_an_Obstacle_to_Teaching_Modern_Law_Students Also see West, R. (2011, December 15). *Rethinking how the law is taught*. The New York Times. Retrieved March 28, 2022, from <https://www.nytimes.com/roomfordebate/2011/12/15/rethinking-how-the-law-is-taught/socratic-teaching-is-a-thing-of-the-past>

[63] Cohen, J. (2015). Work-life balance: *We are focusing on the wrong words*. Bizjournals.com. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.bizjournals.com/philadelphia/blog/guest-comment/2014/10/work-life-balance-we-re-focusing-on-the-wrong.html> Learning that fits the demands of Gen Z enables them to pursue other aspects of life that they deem important.-+

[64] Lederman, D. (2020). *Inside higher ed. One option for delivering instruction if campuses open this fall: HyFlex*. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.insidehighered.com/digital-learning/article/2020/05/13/one-option-delivering-instruction-if-campuses-open-fall-hyflex>.

[65] O'Dowd, R. (2021, June 3). What do students learn in Virtual Exchange? A qualitative content analysis of learning outcomes across multiple exchanges. *International Journal of Educational Research*. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0883035521000744>. Transnational and telecollaborative models of virtual exchange were compared in this study.

[66] United Nations. (2015).

[67] SUNY COIL. *About SUNY Coil*. SUNY COIL Center. (n.d.). Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://coil.suny.edu/about-suny-coil/>. The mission is to make international and intercultural experiences within reach of every student at every institution. COIL is just one of several virtual exchange programs available. Both authors have had extensive experience with this learning paradigm.

[68] Stevens Initiative. (2022, January 8). Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://www.stevensinitiative.org>. Both authors were Stevens Initiative grant recipients enabling

travel to MENA partner countries to discuss collaborative projects. To date, Stevens has awarded 86 grants. By summer 2023, Stevens will expand to nearly 75,000 young people in 17 MENA countries and the Palestinian Territories, 48 U.S. states, Puerto Rico, one tribal community, the U.S. Virgin Islands, and Washington, D.C.

[69] IREX. Investing in people. inspiring change. IREX. (n.d.). Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://www.irex.org>. Along with its partners, IREX works around the globe in 120 countries offering various programs that develop soft skills, empower youth, and provide access to quality education. Global Solutions is a program that is supported by the Stevens Initiative and its partners.

[70] United Nations. (2015).

[71] Author of this paper, Catherine Roche, participated in *Global Solutions* and the team won second place.

[72] Mintz, S. (2021). *Decolonizing the Academy: Inside Higher Ed*. Higher Ed Gamma. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from https://www.insidehighered.com/blogs/higher-ed-gamma/decolonizing-academy?utm_source=Inside%2BHigher%2BEd&utm_campaign=6aee3317a6-

[73] Cherukuvada, S. (2021, July 6). *The gen Z take on Decolonization*. JUV Consulting. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.juvconsulting.com/gen-z-decolonization/>

[74] Mintz, S. (2021).

[75] Mintz, S. (2021).

[76] El-Amin, A., Aaliyah El-Amin Scott Seider Daren Graves Jalene Tamerat Shelby Clark Madora Soutter Jamie Johannsen Saira Malhotra AALIYAH EL-AMIN (aa, Seider, S., Graves, D., Tamerat, J., Clark, S., Soutter, M., Johannsen, J., Malhotra, S., Anderson, R. E., Faulkner, V., Richardson, J., Cokley, K., Pringle, K., Fagell, P. L., Starr, J. P., Ferguson, M., Kim, R., McIntosh, K. M., ... Russo, A. (2020, December 10). *Critical consciousness: A key to student achievement*. kappanonline.org. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://kappanonline.org/critical-consciousness-key-student-achievement/>

[77] El-Amin, A., et al. (2020, December 10). Also see Biin, D., Simcoe, J., Erickson, M., Antoine, A.-na-hi, Cull, I., Hancock, R. L. A., McKeown, S., Pidgeon, M., & Vedan, A. (2018, September 5). *Accessibility statement. Pulling Together A Guide for FrontLine Staff Student Services and Advisors*. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://opentextbc.ca/indigenizationfrontlineworkers/front-matter/accessibility-statement/>

[78] Mintz, S. (2021).

[79] Walpita, S. (2020). *It's time to decolonise education, say gen Z*. The Future Laboratory. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.thefuturelaboratory.com/blog/its-time-to-decolonise-education-say-gen-z> See also James, F. (2021, March 1). Why we need to talk about

the decolonization of Higher Education. QS. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.qs.com/why-we-need-to-talk-about-the-decolonization-of-higher-education>

[80] George, J. (2021). *A Lesson on Critical Race Theory*. Americanbar.org. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from https://www.americanbar.org/groups/crsj/publications/human_rights_magazine_home/civil-rights-reimagining-policing/a-lesson-on-critical-race-theory/

[81] Civil Rights Act of 1964, Pub.L. 88-352, 78 Stat. 241 (1964). Also see Fair Fight Initiative. Critical race theory. Fair Fight Initiative. (n.d.). Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.fairfightinitiative.org/critical-race-theory/>. The Civil Rights Act of 1964 was established to correct historical racial inequities. However, the Act did not fulfill its mission. The Fair Fight Initiative aims to address and end systemic racism in the U.S.

[82] George, J. (2021).

[83] UW College of Education. (2020, July 7). *Geneva gay: A legacy of elevating multicultural education to prominence*. Geneva Gay: A legacy of elevating multicultural education to prominence | UW College of Education. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://education.uw.edu/news/geneva-gay-elevating-multicultural-education-prominence>.

References

Aatbs. (2019, May 16). *The need for emotional intelligence in our youth*. AATBS. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://aatbs.com/blog/post/the-need-for-emotional-intelligence-in-our-youth>

Adichie, C. N. (2009, July) *The danger of a single story*. Facing History and Ourselves. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.facinghistory.org/holocaust-and-human-behavior/chapter-1/danger-single-story>

AFS Intercultural Programs. (2017). *Collaboration, empathy and self-awareness are key skills ...* AFS Intercultural Programs. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://afs.org/2017/04/19/collaboration-empathy-and-self-awareness-are-key-skills-of-global-citizens-an-afs-forum-concludes/>

Belfi, E., & Sandiford, N. (2021). *Decolonization Series Part 1: Exploring Decolonization*. In S. Brandauer and E. Hartman (Eds.). *Interdependence: Global Solidarity and Local Actions. The Community-based Global Learning Collaborative*. Interdependence: Global Solidarity and Local Actions. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://globalsolidaritylocalaction.sites.haverford.edu/what-is-decolonization-why-is-it-important/>

Biin, D., Simcoe, J., Erickson, M., Antoine, A.-na-hi, Cull, I., Hancock, R. L. A., McKeown, S., Pidgeon, M., & Vedan, A. (2018, September 5). *Accessibility statement*. Pulling Together A Guide

for FrontLine Staff Student Services and Advisors. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://opentextbc.ca/indigenizationfrontlineworkers/front-matter/accessibility-statement/>

Bloom, D. (2019, October 6). *How gen Z and millennials are reshaping what power is, and what it means for brands*. Forbes. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/dbloom/2019/09/12/how-gen-z-and-millennials-are-reshaping-what-power-is-and-what-it-means-for-brands/?sh=726d434f6d9f>

Bloomberg. (2021, February 3). *Majority of Generation Z investors identify Green and Sustainable investing as the biggest trend of 2021*. Bloomberg.com. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://www.bloomberg.com/company/press/majority-of-generation-z-investors-identify-green-and-sustainable-investing-as-the-biggest-trend-of-2021/>

Bradberry, T. (2017). *Emotional intelligence: What it is and Why you need it*. World Economic Forum. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2017/02/why-you-need-emotional-intelligence/>

Bradenburger, A., & Nalebuff, B. (2020, December 15). *The rules of co-opetition*. Harvard Business Review. Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://hbr.org/2021/01/the-rules-of-co-opetition>

Brown, H., Guskin, E., & Mitchell, A. (2019, December 31). *The role of social media in the arab uprisings*. Pew Research Center's Journalism Project. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.pewresearch.org/journalism/2012/11/28/role-social-media-arab-uprisings/>

Captain, S. (2021, September 15). *How occupy wall street spawned a decade of protest, politics, and Social Media*. Fast Company. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.fastcompany.com/90675586/occupy-wall-street-tenth-anniversary>

Celeste. (2019, November 30). *How millennials and gen Z are investing sustainably*. How Millennials and Gen Z are investing sustainably. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://inyova.ch/en/expertise/en/millennials-gen-z-and-sustainable-investing/>

Cheng, Y. (2021, May 6). *What is 'coopetition' and how can international organizations help?* World Economic Forum. Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/05/what-is-coopetition-and-how-can-international-organizations-help/>

Cherukuvada, S. (2021, July 6). *The gen Z take on Decolonization*. JUV Consulting. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.juvconsulting.com/gen-z-decolonization/>

Chohan, S. (n.d.). *Influencer marketing for gen Z: 4 keys to success*. linkfluence.png. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.linkfluence.com/blog/influencer-marketing-for-gen-z>

Civil Rights Act of 1964, Pub.L. 88-352, 78 Stat. 241 (1964).

Cohen, J. (2015). *Work-life balance: We are focusing on the wrong words*. Bizjournals.com. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.bizjournals.com/philadelphia/blog/guest-comment/2014/10/work-life-balance-we-re-focusing-on-the-wrong.html>

Contemporary Education. (2019). *What is the Contemporary Education Framework?* Contemporary Education. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <http://www.contemporaryeducation.com/2019/07/what-is-contemporary-education-framework.html>

Cranley, E. (2019, October 1). *These 10 young activists are trying to move the Needle on climate change, gun control, and other global issues*. Insider. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.insider.com/young-activists-climate-change-guns-greta-thunberg-2019-9>

Dans, E. (2020, September 15). *You are wrong if you think generation Z is "Immune" to fake news*. Forbes. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/enriquedans/2020/09/15/you-are-wrong-if-you-think-generation-z-is-immune-to-fake-news/?sh=331e5414314e>

De Leersnyder, J., Boiger, M., & Mesquita, B. (2013). Cultural regulation of emotion: individual, relational, and structural sources. *Frontiers in psychology*, 4, 55. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00055>

Dodman, B. (2019, November 16). *A year of insurgency: How yellow vests left 'indelible mark' on French politics*. France 24. Retrieved March 29, 2022, from <https://www.france24.com/en/20191116-a-year-of-insurgency-how-yellow-vests-left-indelible-mark-on-french-politics>

El-Amin, A., Aaliyah El-Amin Scott Seider Daren Graves Jalene Tamerat Shelby Clark Madora Soutter Jamie Johannsen Saira Malhotra AALIYAH EL-AMIN (aa, Seider, S., Graves, D., Tamerat, J., Clark, S., Soutter, M., Johannsen, J., Malhotra, S., Anderson, R. E., Faulkner, V., Richardson, J., Cokley, K., Pringle, K., Fagell, P. L., Starr, J. P., Ferguson, M., Kim, R., McIntosh, K. M., ... Russo, A. (2020, December 10). *Critical consciousness: A key to student achievement*. kappanonline.org. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://kappanonline.org/critical-consciousness-key-student-achievement/>

The elevator project. the elevator project. (n.d.). Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.theelevatorproject.org/>

Fair Fight Initiative. *Critical race theory*. Fair Fight Initiative. (n.d.). Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.fairfightinitiative.org/critical-race-theory/>

Finch, J. (2015, May 4). *What is generation Z, and what does it want?* Fast Company. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.fastcompany.com/3045317/what-is-generation-z-and-what-does-it->

[want?_hstc=221473223.0fa5c0f39c269721a12412d24af07c14.1635074976953.1635074976953.1635074976953.1&_hssc=221473223.1.1635074976953&_hsfp=110276527](https://www.businessinsider.com/protests-activism-professor-why-george-floyd-movement-is-different-2020-6)

Fisher, D. (2020, June 7). *I'm a professor who studies protests and activism. here's why the George Floyd protests are different.* Business Insider. Retrieved March 29, 2022, from <https://www.businessinsider.com/protests-activism-professor-why-george-floyd-movement-is-different-2020-6>

Freer, A. (2020, March 8). *89% of young people follow 'relatable' influencers.* Business of Apps. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://www.businessofapps.com/news/89-of-young-people-follow-relatable-influencers/>

Fry, R., & Parker, K. (2020, August 14). *'post-millennial' generation on track to be most diverse, best-educated.* Pew Research Center's Social & Demographic Trends Project. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.pewresearch.org/social-trends/2018/11/15/early-benchmarks-show-post-millennials-on-track-to-be-most-diverse-best-educated-generation-yet/>

George, J. (2021). *A Lesson on Critical Race Theory.* Americanbar.org. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from https://www.americanbar.org/groups/crsj/publications/human_rights_magazine_home/civil-rights-reimagining-policing/a-lesson-on-critical-race-theory/

Gerstmann, E. (2021, December 10). *Cancel culture is only getting worse.* Forbes. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/evangerstmann/2020/09/13/cancel-culture-is-only-getting-worse/?sh=3a509b9463f4>

Grimes, D. R. (2016, November 8). *Impartial journalism is laudable. but false balance is dangerous.* The Guardian. Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.theguardian.com/science/blog/2016/nov/08/impartial-journalism-is-laudable-but-false-balance-is-dangerous>

Henderson, R. (2021, November 18). *America exports cancel culture to the world.* Quillette. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://quillette.com/2020/07/02/america-exports-cancel-culture-to-the-world/>

Hohaia, M. (2019, September 26). *Emotional intelligence: No longer a 'nice to have' but an essential skill in the workplace.* Thrive Global. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://thriveglobal.com/stories/emotional-intelligence-no-longer-a-nice-to-have-but-an-essential-skill-in-the-workplace/>

Hughes, E. (2020, January 10). *The future of work is creative collaboration.* Management. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.management-issues.com/opinion/7369/the-future-of-work-is-creative-collaboration/>

IREX. *Investing in people. inspiring change.* IREX. (n.d.). Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://www.irex.org>

James, F. (2021, March 1). *Why we need to talk about the decolonization of Higher Education.* QS. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.qs.com/why-we-need-to-talk-about-the-decolonization-of-higher-education>

Ko, D. (2021, January). *How gen Z redefines media consumption habits - think with google apac.* Google. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/intl/en-apac/consumer-insights/consumer-trends/stay-woke-how-gen-z-teaching-us-about-future-news-and-information/>

Landau, J. (2018, October 17). *Council post: Why cultural sensitivity should be a forethought, not an afterthought.* Forbes. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesnycouncil/2018/10/17/why-cultural-sensitivity-should-be-a-forethought-not-an-afterthought/>

Lederman, D. (2020). *Inside higher ed.* One option for delivering instruction if campuses open this fall: HyFlex. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.insidehighered.com/digital-learning/article/2020/05/13/one-option-delivering-instruction-if-campuses-open-fall-hyflex>

Levy, F., & Murnane, R. J. (2006). *Why the changing American economy calls for twenty-first century learning: answers to educators' questions.* Europe PMC. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://europepmc.org/article/med/17017257>

Li, E. (2018, August 20). *The rise and fall of Soft Power.* Foreign Policy. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://foreignpolicy.com/2018/08/20/the-rise-and-fall-of-soft-power>

Lii, B. (2008, September). *(PDF) the Elephant in law school classrooms: Overuse of ...* The Elephant in Law School Classrooms: Overuse of the Socratic Method as an Obstacle to Teaching Modern Law Students. Retrieved March 29, 2022, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228155379_The_Elephant_in_Law_School_Classrooms_Overuse_of_the_Socratic_Method_as_an_Obstacle_to_Teaching_Modern_Law_Students

Lichfield, J. (2019, February 9). *Just who are the gilets jaunes?* The Guardian. Retrieved March 27, 2022, from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/feb/09/who-really-are-the-gilets-jaunes>

Luttrell, R., & McGrath, K. (2021). *Gen Z: The superhero generation.* Rowman & Littlefield.

McGrath, M. (2021, June 29). *From activist to author: How 12-year-old Marley Dias is changing the face of Children's Literature.* Forbes. Retrieved March 29, 2022, from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/maggiemcgrath/2017/06/13/from-activist-to-author-how-12-year-old-marley-dias-is-changing-the-face-of-childrens-literature/?sh=41ffb9e44ce0>

Miladinovic, M. (2018, August 28). *Emotional intelligence is the basis for global competence*. carlostest2. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://carloestest2.afssite.afs.org/2018/05/15/emotional-intelligence-is-the-basis-for-global-competence/?lang=en>

Mintz, S. (2021). *Decolonizing the Academy: Inside Higher Ed*. Higher Ed Gamma. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from https://www.insidehighered.com/blogs/higher-ed-gamma/decolonizing-academy?utm_source=Inside%2BHigher%2BEd&utm_campaign=6aee3317a6-

National Geographic Society. (2012, October 9). *The global network*. National Geographic Society. Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/article/global-network/>

National Geographic Society. (n.d.). *Geo-education: Essential preparation for an interconnected world*. National Geographic Society. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.nationalgeographic.org/education/geo-education-essential-preparation-interconnected-world/>

O'Dowd, R. (2021, June 3). *What do students learn in Virtual Exchange? A qualitative content analysis of learning outcomes across multiple exchanges*. International Journal of Educational Research. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0883035521000744>

Osmundsen, M., Petersen, M. B., & Bor, A. (2021, May 13). *How partisan polarization drives the spread of fake news*. Brookings. Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.brookings.edu/techstream/how-partisan-polarization-drives-the-spread-of-fake-news>

Oxfam. (2021). *What is global citizenship*. Oxfam GB. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.oxfam.org.uk/education/who-we-are/what-is-global-citizenship/>

Oxfam Australia. *What she makes*. Oxfam Australia. (2021, December 6). Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.oxfam.org.au/what-she-makes/>

Pasquarella Daley, L., Van Bommel, T., & Brassel, S. (2020). *Why empathy is a superpower in the future of Work - Catalyst*. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from https://www.catalyst.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Catalyst_Empathy-Primer_Final.pdf

Peers J. (2021, July 15). *Gen Z: Who else?* Natixis Investment Managers. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.im.natixis.com/us/esg/gen-z-who-else>

PISA. (2018). *Global competence - PISA*. OECD. Retrieved January 7, 2022, from <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/innovation/global-competence/>

Pretorius, Q., Merry, T., & Center, C. I. (2021, November 8). *Cultural intelligence training: Cultural intelligence center*. Cultural Intelligence Center - We provide research-based, innovative

solutions for assessing, predicting, and improving cultural intelligence (CQ). Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://culturalq.com/about-cultural-intelligence/culture/>

Salukov, D. (2021, December 7). *Gen Z Influencer Marketing: Everything you need to know*. Insense. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://insense.pro/blog/gen-z-influencer-marketing-everything-you-need-to-know>

Sawyer, A. (2021). *What businesses and gen Z have to offer each other*. World Economic Forum. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/06/business-education-gen-z-global-challenges-future>

Simmons A. (2017, March 8). *Q&A: United Arab Emirates' 23-year-old minister of Youth Affairs has high aspirations for her peers*. Los Angeles Times. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.latimes.com/world/global-development/la-fg-global-uae-youth-minister-20170302-story.html>

Statista Research Department, & 14, O. (2021, October 14). *Global Influencer Market Size 2021*. Statista. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1092819/global-influencer-market-size/>

Stevens Initiative. (2022, January 8). Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://www.stevensinitiative.org>

Sunrise Movement. *We are the Climate Revolution*. Sunrise Movement. (2021, December 15). Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.sunrisemovement.org/>

SUNY COIL. *About SUNY Coil*. SUNY COIL Center. (n.d.). Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://coil.suny.edu/about-suny-coil/>

Thomas, D. (2019, August 29). *The high price of Fast Fashion*. The Wall Street Journal. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from https://www.wsj.com/articles/the-high-price-of-fast-fashion-11567096637?mod=article_inline

United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development | department of economic and social affairs*. United Nations. Retrieved January 8, 2022, from <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>

UW College of Education. (2020, July 7). *Geneva gay: A legacy of elevating multicultural education to prominence*. Geneva Gay: A legacy of elevating multicultural education to prominence | UW College of Education. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://education.uw.edu/news/geneva-gay-elevating-multicultural-education-prominence>

Vander Ark, T. (2017, September 5). *Educating for global competence: 6 reasons, 7 competencies, 8 strategies, 9 innovations*. Getting Smart. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from

<https://www.gettingsmart.com/2017/09/05/educating-for-global-competence-6-reasons-7-competencies-8-strategies-9-innovations/>

Walpita, S. (2020). *It's time to decolonise education, say gen Z*. The Future Laboratory. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://www.thefuturelaboratory.com/blog/its-time-to-decolonise-education-say-gen-z>

Walt, V. (2020, December 11). *Assa Traoré and France's fight for racial justice*. Time. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://time.com/5919814/guardians-of-the-year-2020-assa-traore/>

West, R. (2011, December 15). *Rethinking how the law is taught*. The New York Times. Retrieved March 28, 2022, from <https://www.nytimes.com/roomfordebate/2011/12/15/rethinking-how-the-law-is-taught/socratic-teaching-is-a-thing-of-the-past>

Woodbury, R. (2021, June 9). *A guide to gen Z through TikTok trends, Emojis, & language*. Digital Native. Retrieved December 18, 2021, from <https://digitalnative.substack.com/p/a-guide-to-gen-z-through-tiktok-trends>

Wulfhorst, E. (2020, July 9). *How Generation Z is Propelling the Black Lives Matter Movement*. Two River Times. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://tworivertimes.com/how-generation-z-is-propelling-the-black-lives-matter-movement/>

Yuan, L. (2019, August 20). *China's soft-power failure: Condemning Hong Kong's protests*. The New York Times. Retrieved December 17, 2021, from <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/08/20/business/china-hong-kong-social-media-soft-power.html>